

Muster

für einen Abschlussbericht in der Einzelförderung: Programm Sachbeihilfe

ABSCHLUSSBERICHT

1 Allgemeine Angaben

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Projektnummer: 671414

Titel des Projekts: Scrutinizing an epigenetic driven dysregulation of prefrontal mGluR2 function in alcohol dependence

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2 Zusammenfassung / Summary

Dieses Projekt untersuchte, ob Alkoholabhängigkeit zu präfrontalen Defiziten führt, die durch epigenetische Störungen der mGluR2-Funktion vermittelt werden und letztlich die exekutive Kontrolle und Rückfallneigung beeinträchtigen. Im Rahmen von Ziel 1 konnte gezeigt werden, dass alkoholabhängige Ratten Einschränkungen in der Entscheidungsfindung aufweisen, die durch die Wiederherstellung der mGluR2-Expression im infralimbischen Kortex rückgängig gemacht werden konnten. Obwohl im Rahmen von Ziel 2 erfolgreich Protokolle zur Analyse der DNA-Methylierung und der Bindung von Transkriptionsfaktoren am mGluR2-Promotor im Gesamthirngewebe etabliert wurden, verhinderten technische Limitierungen diese Analysen in isolierten neuronalen Populationen. Als ergänzender Ansatz wurden die Effekte von Psilocybin untersucht: Dabei zeigte sich, dass Psilocybin die mGluR2-Expression in Tiermodellen erhöhte, was teilweise mit einer Reduktion repressiver Histonmodifikationen einherging. Klinische Methylom-Analysen bei AUD-Patienten, die mit Psilocybin behandelt wurden, ergaben darüber hinaus Methylierungsveränderungen in Genen, die mit Neuroplastizität und Immunfunktionen assoziiert sind, was mögliche Mechanismen hinter dem Behandlungserfolg andeutet. Zusammenfassend lieferte das Projekt wertvolle Einblicke in die Rolle von mGluR2 bei Alkoholabhängigkeit und eröffnete neue Wege für translationale Forschung.

This project investigated whether alcohol dependence leads to prefrontal deficits driven by epigenetic disruption of mGluR2 function, ultimately affecting executive control and relapse. Aim 1 demonstrated that alcohol-dependent rats exhibit impaired decision-making, which could be reversed by restoring mGluR2 expression in the infralimbic cortex. Although Aim 2 successfully established protocols to analyze DNA methylation and transcription factor binding at the mGluR2 promoter in bulk tissue, technical limitations prevented these analyses in purified neuronal populations. As a complementary approach, the team explored psilocybin's effects, finding that it increased mGluR2 expression in rodent models, partly through reduced repressive histone marks. Clinical methylome analyses in alcohol use disorder (AUD) patients treated with psilocybin revealed additional methylation changes in genes linked to neuroplasticity and immune function, suggesting potential mechanisms underlying treatment response. Collectively, the project provided valuable insights into mGluR2's role in alcohol dependence and opened new translational research avenues.

3 Wissenschaftlicher Arbeits- und Ergebnisbericht

The working hypothesis of this proposal was that a history of alcohol dependence engenders a prefrontal deficit, leading to an epigenetic driven disruption of mGluR2 function, which ultimately causes a deterioration in executive function and relapse to alcohol. The overall strategy of this proposal was to test this hypothesis with the following three aims:

- Aim 1: To establish the effect of a prefrontal mGluR2 deficit on executive control.
- Aim 2: To determine the degree of epigenetic modification at the Grm2 gene in purified neuronal populations of the prefrontal cortex in alcohol dependent rats.
- Aim 3: To study the effect of site-specific epigenetic modifiers to rescue the behavioral phenotype in alcohol dependent rats

Here we primarily report on the work of the first two aims, as the third was not considered for funding by the DFG Fachkollegium.

The research data collected in the project are archived in our electronic lab notebook (eLab-FTW). The data is stored in accordance with the FAIR principles and complies with the DFG guidelines on good scientific practice. The data is stored in a structured manner, documented in a traceable manner and accessible to authorized persons in the long term.

Results of aim 1

In this aim, we investigated whether postdependent rats, which exhibit an infralimbic mGluR2 deficit, show additional cognitive impairments beyond set shifting by employing the delay discounting task. Consistent with our hypothesis, postdependent rats demonstrated significant cognitive deficits: alcohol-dependent rats displayed a steeper discounting curve, indicating a more rapid shift in preference toward the smaller, immediate reward over the larger, delayed reward. These findings were published in Meinhardt et al., 2021, figure 1B,C. To directly link the observed deficits to mGluR2 function, we examined whether restoring mGluR2 expression within the infralimbic cortex could normalize cognitive flexibility. Using a lentiviral overexpression approach in 32 alcohol-dependent Wistar rats (Meinhardt et al., 2021, Figure 1F,G), we successfully rescued mGluR2 levels. As illustrated in Figure 1H, this intervention reversed the cognitive impairments observed in alcohol-dependent rats.

Taken together, these results highlight the critical role of infralimbic mGluR2 signaling in mediating decision-making processes compromised by alcohol dependence.

Identification of potential *egr2* binding sites on the *GRM2* promoter

Three potential binding sites of the transcription factor *egr2* were predicted near the *Grm2* promoter (Fig. 2A). All three are found on the antisense strand and have a length of 19bp. The exact location based on the current annotation release (108, mRatBN7.2) is: 107293264-107293246, 107293214-107293196 and 107293212-107293194 (chromosome 8). Several primer pairs were constructed within the displayed range and tested for further usage. The best results were obtained for CCTGTCAAGAGCGGGATCTG as forward primer and CTCTGTTCCTCTGGACTCCC as reverse primer (data not shown).

ChIP optimization to study transcription factor binding to the *Grm2* promoter

To demonstrate the binding of *Egr2* to the proposed sites on the *Grm2* promoter, the ChIP protocol first had to be established. One critical challenge in ChIP is optimizing the shearing conditions to generate appropriately sized DNA fragments. To assess this, DNA before and after shearing was visualized on a 1% agarose gel, where a clear smear ranging from ~400 bp to ~1500 bp was observed (Fig. 2B). To further optimize fragment length, several shearing conditions were tested by varying pulse settings, durations, and power levels, with the results again analyzed by gel electrophoresis (Fig. 3C). Following successful shearing, qPCR amplification was performed using previously validated primers, including melt curve analysis on three replicates each of the 2% input and immunoprecipitated (IP) samples. As shown in Figure 2A, the input samples had a Ct value of approximately 28, while the IP samples showed a Ct value around 38, indicating a difference of roughly 10 cycles. Given that a 10-fold dilution corresponds to a Ct shift of about 3.3 cycles, this suggests that the input samples contained approximately 1000 times more *Grm2* promoter region than the IP samples. Importantly, melt curve analysis revealed specific amplification at a melting temperature (T_m) of 85°C for both input and IP samples. In summary, the ChIP protocol was successfully established for bulk tissue, enabling reliable detection of *Egr2* binding to the *Grm2* promoter region.

Figure 2: ChIP troubleshooting to investigate potential binding of *egr2* to the *GRM2* promoter. Brain tissue from male Sprague Dawley rats was used to perform the ChIP experiments. (A) Potential *egr2* binding sites on the *GRM2* promoter were predicted using the MatInspector tool. Potential binding sites are depicted in green and the used range for primer design in red. (B) Chromatin before and after hydrodynamic shearing was visualized by gel electrophoreses. (C) Different shearing conditions were used to optimize the shearing step. The sheared chromatin was visualised by 1% agarose gel electrophoresis. The gel was stained with ethidium bromide and visualized with UV light. (D) Specific qPCR amplification of input and immunoprecipitated samples.

Isolation of tdTomato-positive cells from the mPFC of frozen rat brains

Following the establishment of both methods, double transgenic CamK2a-iCRE x nuc-tdTomato male Sprague Dawley rats were bred for experiments (n=16). Half of the animals were treated by 7 weeks of alcohol vapor exposure followed by 3 weeks of abstinence while the other half was used as control. After this time brains were extracted and frozen for cell isolation via Fluorescence-Activated Cell Sorting (FACS), see figure 3 for the experimental time line.

Figure 3: Experimental background and setup. tdTomato-positive cells were isolated by fluorescence-activated cell sorting (FACS) from CamK2a-iCRE x nuc-tdTomato transgenic male Sprague Dawley rats (n= 16). Half of the animals were treated by 7 weeks of alcohol vapor exposure followed by 3 weeks of abstinence while the other half was used as control. (A) The CamK2 alpha promoter drives the expression of the improved Cre (iCre) recombinase gene. (B) In presence of iCre, nuc-tdTomato fluorescent dye gets expressed due to Cre-mediated recombination and deletes the SNAPf-tag gene. (C) The depicted timeline of the conducted experiments shows the duration of alcohol vapor exposure and abstinence for the treated animals (n=8). Weeks indicate the age of the animals. (D) The workflow demonstrates the single steps that were carried out in order to isolate DNA and RNA from the desired cells of the rat brain for further experiments.

First, fluorescence microscopy was performed to confirm the expression of tdTomato in the brains of CamK2a-iCRE x nuc-tdTomato transgenic animals. Images obtained from 20 μm brain sections showed a clear and robust tdTomato signal localized to the nuclei of several cells (Fig. 4B). Next, 100 μm brain slices were prepared, and the medial prefrontal cortex (mPFC) was microdissected based on anatomical landmarks from the Rat Brain Atlas (Fig. 4A). This and all subsequent procedures were carried out individually for all vapor-exposed ($n=8$) and control ($n=8$) animals. The amount of harvested mPFC tissue varied between 12 mg and 27 mg per brain, depending on the animal's size (Fig. 4C). The dissected tissue was then processed into single-cell suspensions for fluorescence-activated cell sorting (FACS). The gating strategy, illustrated in Fig. 4E and Fig. 4F, allowed for a clear separation between tdTomato-positive and tdTomato-negative cells from transgenic and wild-type animals, respectively. Among all FACS events, 0.5% were sorted as tdTomato-positive and 1.4% as tdTomato-negative cells. On average, about 15,000 tdTomato-positive cells were isolated per sample, although the number ranged widely from 3,000 to 65,000 cells (Fig. 4D). By comparison, tdTomato-negative cells yielded an average of approximately 50,000 cells (data not shown). RNA and DNA were extracted from tdTomato-negative cells of two control and two vapor-exposed animals, and their quality was assessed: RNA was reverse-transcribed to cDNA and amplified with GAPDH and GRM2 primer pairs, while DNA was amplified using GAPDH and ROSA primer pairs. As shown in Fig. 2G, clear bands at the expected sizes were obtained for nearly all samples, confirming successful extraction and amplification. In summary, tdTomato expression and the applied FACS protocol reliably enabled the isolation and downstream validation of defined neuronal cell populations from the mPFC. The extracted DNA was further used epigenetic investigations of DNA methylation changes as well as Egr2-Grm2 ChIP. Samples of two individual rats were pooled in order to increase total DNA. However, neither the amplification of DNA products after bisulfite treatment for DNA methylation analysis nor the amplification of input or IP samples from the ChIP workflow was successful, likely due to the very limited amount of starting material. As a result, it was unfortunately not possible to analyze epigenetic modifications at the Grm2 gene in purified neuronal populations from the prefrontal cortex of alcohol-dependent rats.

Figure 4: Isolation of tdTomato-positive and tdTomato-negative cells from the mPFC and quality control of extracted DNA and RNA. Brain tissue from post-dependent and control *CamK2a-iCRE x nuc-tdTomato* transgenic male Sprague Dawley rats ($n=8$, respectively) was used for fluorescence-activated cell sorting (FACS).

(A) 100 μ m brain slices from frozen rat brains were obtained with the cryostat and the medial prefrontal cortex (mPFC) punched (pink area). (B) Expression and localization of tdTomato in the cells of the PFC was confirmed by fluorescent microscopy using 10x air objective. The average amount of mPFC obtained by the rat brains (C) as well as the average number of cells isolated by FACS (D) is depicted with a boxplot. (E) Single cells were identified by plotting forward scatter-area against forward scatter-height (plot I). Furthermore, the gating strategy to distinguish tdTomato-positive from tdTomato-negative cells is shown for both transgenic and wildtype animals. (F) Gating hierarchy. (G) Quality

control of isolated DNA (right) and RNA (left) was performed by PCR and RT-PCR followed by PCR, respectively. The products were visualised by 1% agarose gel electrophoresis. DNA and RNA was used from tdTomato-negative cells of 2 vapor exposed (261 and 270) and 2 control (250 and 253) animals. The gel was stained with ethidium bromide and visualized with UV light.

Follow-up experiments on pharmacological restoration of the behavioral disease phenotype

Following the disappointing results, we set out to explore an mGluR2 mechanism-based intervention with high translational potential. Psychedelics such as psilocybin have been shown to promote effects on G-protein coupled signal transduction as well as downstream effectors, second messengers, and gene expression. Altered or reduced signaling in downstream pathways linked to the primary target (5-HT_{2A}R) could in turn increase transmission via mGluR2 due to the reciprocally inhibitory relationship between 5-HT_{2A}R and mGluR2.

Accordingly, we first investigated whether psilocybin is capable to modulate gene expression levels in naïve Wistar rats. In this experiment, we analyzed gene expression in the nucleus accumbens of rats 4 hours after receiving either psilocybin (1 mg/kg; i.p.), a 5-HT_{2A}R antagonist ketanserin (0.12 µg; i.c.v.) or the combination psilocybin/ketanserin with an custom RT2 ProfilerTM PCR arrays, containing sets of rat neurotransmission-specific genes. The results of this experiment are summarized in Meinhardt et al. 2021, figure 5A. Screening of neurotransmission genes demonstrated alteration in the expression of several candidate genes following psilocybin i.p. injection in naive rats. Importantly, among the genes most strongly upregulated in the psilocybin group was *Grm2* (fold-change: 2.35). Moreover, this upregulation seems 5-HT_{2A}R dependent, as ketanserin blocks this change in gene expression in the psilocybin/ketanserin group. We next evaluated whether psilocybin could also increase *Grm2* levels in alcohol-dependent rats. As expected by our previous results, alcohol-dependent rats showed a significant two-fold decrease of accumbal *Grm2* expression. Psilocybin i.p. treatment restored *Grm2* expression to vehicle control levels (Meinhardt et al. 2021, figure 5B). No change of *Htr2a* gene expression was observed (Meinhardt et al. 2021, figure 5C).

Finally, we wanted to know if this molecular mGluR2 rescue with psilocybin could also reduce relapse to alcohol. Psilocybin (1 and 2.5 mg/kg) or vehicle (0 mg/kg) were administered 4 hours prior to the relapse session. We observed a highly significant dose but no dose-response effect with similar reduction in relapse for alcohol with both doses of psilocybin as compared to the vehicle.

Based on these very promising results, we further explored how psilocybin may increase mGluR2 expression and if epigenetic mechanisms might be involved (Figure 5). Using human induced pluripotent stem cells (hiPSCs) that were differentiated into cortical neurons, we found a reduction in H3k27me3 of the mGluR2 gene (*Grm2*) promoter region 24h after a short psilocybin treatment (see figure below 1d + 10mM). H3K27me3 is an epigenetic modification to the DNA packaging protein Histone H3. It is a mark that indicates the tri-methylation of lysine 27 on histone H3 protein. This tri-methylation is associated with the downregulation of nearby genes via the formation of heterochromatic regions. Therefore, the observed reduction in H3k27me3 could lead to an increase/rescue of mGluR2 levels.

Figure 5: Epigenetic H3k27me3 analysis of the mGluR2 gene (*Grm2*) promoter region 248bp upstream of the transcription start site in hiPSCs. Three different treatments were compared to a control condition (no psilocybin application): 1: Harvest after one day post 10minutes bath with 10 μ M psilocybin; 2: Three days post 10minutes 10 μ M psilocybin or 3: Three days post 6h 100nM psilocybin bath.

Building on these results, we further explored whether psilocybin was also able to modify the DNA methylation in blood of AUD patients that received psilocybin treatment (manuscript under consideration at *translational psychiatry* and as preprint at bioRxiv Urban et al. 2025). Thus, blood samples of the clinical samples were processed on an Infinium MethylationEPIC BeadChip for whole methylome analysis of all time points (t1= baseline measurement during abstinence, 14 days after the cessation of alcohol drinking, t2= 2days after psilocybin, t3= 4week post treatment).

We identified one CpG site in TLE4 ($p = 1.1e-7$) associated with psilocybin treatment. Screening for differentially methylated regions, we observed altered methylation in the gene RASGRP4 ($pFDR = 3.2e-4$). Network analysis revealed co-methylation modules related to psilocybin treatment, as well as modules associated with the reduction of depressive symp-

toms and drinking behavior. Gene ontology analysis indicated involvement of these modules in neuroplasticity and immune functions, suggesting that they may reflect abstinence-related recovery processes. Investigating candidate genes at nominal significance ($p < 0.05$) uncovered promoter-associated methylation changes in HTR2A and TNF. Furthermore, at $p < 0.05$, we found baseline differences between treatment responders (< 1 standard unit alcohol in 4-week follow-up) and non-responders in genes related to synaptic plasticity and different neurotransmitter systems. Although these findings are limited by the modest sample size, they align well with previous literature and might provide starting points for further, large-scale investigations or hypothesis-driven experiments.

4 Veröffentlichte Projektergebnisse

4.1 Kategorie A – Fachaufsätze in Peer Review-Zeitschriften, Beiträge zu Konferenzen mit Peer Review oder Sammelbänden sowie Buchpublikationen

1. [Mini-review: The neurobiology of treating substance use disorders with classical psychedelics.](#)

Urban MM, Stingl MR, Meinhardt MW.

Front Neurosci. 2023 Apr 17;17:1156319. doi: 10.3389/fnins.2023.1156319. eCollection 2023.

PMID: 37139521 **Free article.** Review.

2. [Psychedelic Targeting of Metabotropic Glutamate Receptor 2 and Its Implications for the Treatment of Alcoholism.](#)

Domanegg K, Sommer WH, Meinhardt MW.

Cells. 2023 Mar 22;12(6):963. doi: 10.3390/cells12060963.

PMID: 36980303 **Free article.** Review.

3. [Schrooms against booze: Potential of mycotherapy for the treatment of AUD.](#)

Meinhardt MW, Sommer WH.

Neuropsychopharmacology. 2023 Jan;48(1):211-212. doi: 10.1038/s41386-022-01446-7.

PMID: 36076019 **Free article.**

4. [Psilocybin targets a common molecular mechanism for cognitive impairment and increased craving in alcoholism.](#)

Meinhardt MW, Pfarr S, Fouquet G, Rohleder C, Meinhardt ML, Barroso-Flores J, Hoffmann R, Jeanblanc J, Paul E, Wagner K, Hansson AC, Köhr G, Meier N,

von Bohlen Und Halbach O, Bell RL, Endepols H, Neumaier B, Schönig K, Bartsch D, Naassila M, Spanagel R, Sommer WH.
Sci Adv. 2021 Nov 19;7(47):eabh2399. doi: 10.1126/sciadv.abh2399. Epub 2021 Nov 17.
PMID: 34788104 **Free article.**

4.2 Kategorie B – Jede weitere Form öffentlich gemachter Ergebnisse

1. [Epigenome-wide Association Study of Psilocybin-Induced Methylome Changes in Alcohol Use Disorder.](#)

Marvin M. Urban, Lea Zillich, Nathalie M. Rieser, Marcus Herdener, Franz X. Vollenweider, Rainer Spanagel, Katrin H. Preller, Marcus W. Meinhardt
bioRxiv preprint. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2025.07.18.664368>

4.3 Patente (angemeldete und erteilte)

NA

